

Molecular Adsorption of Carboxylic Acids by Anion-Exchange Resin

L. POCHHALI* and S. K. ADHIKARY

Physical Chemistry Section, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700032

and

K. C. RAY

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan, Birbhum, West Bengal, India

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Pure molecular adsorption of carboxylic acids (formic to n-butyric), mono- and dichloroacetic acids and hydrochloric acid has been studied with an anion-exchange resin, Amberlite-IRA-400, in its respective anion forms. The order of molecular adsorption of these acids on the respective anion forms of the resin is, hydrochloric < formic < acetic < propionic < n-butyric < monochloroacetic < dichloroacetic. For the carboxylic acids, molecular adsorption increases with the increase in chain length of the acids.

The adsorption of the strong acid, HCl, is very small. Also it is known that not the carboxylate ions but the undissociated acids are molecularly adsorbed by the resin. But here it is found that the molecular adsorption of the chlorosubstituted acetic acids is considerably higher than the carboxylic acids studied, though the dissociation constants of the chlorosubstituted acetic acids are much greater than those of the carboxylic acids.

Molecular adsorptions of the carboxylic acids by the nitrate, sulphate and chromate forms of the same resin have also been studied. The order of molecular adsorption of these acids by all the salt forms of the anion-exchange resin is the same as obtained for the resin containing the same counter-anions as the acids. The acids are most strongly held by the chromate form of the resin and least strongly by the nitrate form.

SYNTHETIC ion-exchange resins have got the property of adsorbing molecules of non-electrolytes as well as electrolytes, specially weakly dissociated electrolytes like aliphatic carboxylic acids. But in the latter case both ion-exchange and molecular adsorption take place simultaneously, when counter-ion of the resin is different from that in the acid. Some works on adsorption of these acids on cation-exchange resins have been reported by Reichenberg and Wall¹; Starobinets and Kharevich² and others³⁻⁵. Like cation-exchange resins, weak and strong electrolytes are adsorbed by anion-exchange resins. Molecular adsorption of carboxylic acids by anion-exchange resins has been studied recently by Starobinets et al⁶⁻¹⁰. Molecular adsorption of fluoroacetic acids together with acetic acids by anion-exchange resin in its respective ionic forms, have been studied by Samuelson, Soldatov and Thornton¹¹.

Pure molecular adsorption occurs when solution of a particular electrolyte comes in contact with an anion-exchange resin containing counter-ion similar to that present in the electrolyte. In the other forms ion-exchange together with molecular adsorption may also occur. If the resin in R-X form (X is anion of an acid) is equilibrated with an acid of the type HA, then

ion-exchange occurs between X⁻ and A⁻ in the following way,

The decrease in concentration of HA due to ion-exchange is equal to the concentration of the new acid (HX) formed. Hence total concentration of acids in the equilibrium solution will be the same as initial concentration of the acid HA. Any decrease in concentration observed in the equilibrium solution will give the value of molecular adsorption which can be determined from the difference in concentrations of the acids.

In this paper, molecular adsorptions of carboxylic acids, formic to n-butyric, mono- and dichloroacetic and hydrochloric acids by an anion-exchange resin, Amberlite-IRA-400, containing counter-ions similar to those in the acids, have been studied. Similar studies have also been done with formic to n-butyric acids and the same anion-exchange resin in nitrate, sulphate and chromate forms.

* Senior author

Experimental

A monofunctional highly basic quaternary alkylammonium polystyrene resin, Amberlite-IRA-400, cross-linked with 8% divinylbenzene was obtained commercially (manufacturer: Rohm and Haas Co., U.S.A.) in spherical beads. The resin in chloride form was first washed with double distilled water and then transferred into a column. The resin was then converted into OH-form by thorough leaching with about 0.5 *N* NaOH solution. Leaching was continued till the effluent gave no test for chloride with AgNO₃ solution. The resin was then completely washed with double distilled water until the effluent gave no colour with phenolphthalein. The hydroxyl form of the resin was then air-dried at room temperature.

The carboxylates, chloro-acetates, chloride, nitrate and sulphate forms of the resin were prepared from the hydroxyl form by treating with about 1*N* of corresponding acids and then washed carefully with double distilled water to remove the additional acids from the resin. These were checked by conductometric and pH measurements of the effluents. These were then air-dried and kept in closed containers.

The chromate form of the resin was prepared from the hydroxyl form by treating with about 1*N* K₂CrO₄ solution and then washed free from excess K₂CrO₄ with double distilled water, air-dried and kept in a closed container.

Aliphatic acids ranging from formic to n-butyric, mono- and dichloroacetic acids, hydrochloric acid were obtained in pure "analar grades" and so used without any further purification.

Before doing the experiments, the exchange capacity of the resin was found out. The exchange capacity of the resin was determined by two methods; (i) A weighed amount of hydroxyl form of the resin (about 1 gm.) with known moisture content was equilibrated with 0.2*N* HCl solution in a stoppered Jena glass bottle by shaking in a mechanical shaker for 4 hours. The mixture was then kept for 24 hours to attain equilibrium. The solution was then separated from the resin and the unreacted acid was titrated with standard sodium hydroxide solution using phenolphthalein indicator. The amount of acid consumed in the reaction with the resin was obtained by difference in concentrations. This difference gave the exchange capacity of the resin. (ii) In the second method, a weighed quantity of the resin (about 1 gm) in chloride form was taken in a column. About 1*N* NaOH solution was passed through the column. Liberated chloride was estimated by argentometric titration with AgNO₃ solution using fluorescein as an indicator^{1,2}. The exchange capacity per gm of dry resin was calculated from the amount of chloride ion displaced. From these two methods the exchange capacity of the resin, Amberlite-IRA-400, was found to be 2.52 ± 0.02 meq per gm of dry resin.

For determining the molecular adsorption, known amounts (about 1 gm) of the air-dried resin in different salt forms of known moisture content were equilibrated with 50 ml acid solutions of known initial concentrations. In the case of chromate form of the resin, the colour of the resin changed from yellow to orange after adding acid solutions to the resin. This showed that in acid solution, the CrO₄²⁻ ion of the resin was converted into Cr₂O₇²⁻ ion. But for simplicity the term "chromate-resin" will be used in this paper. The mixtures were shaken in a mechanical shaker for 4 hours and then kept for 48 hours to attain equilibrium. The concentrations of the equilibrium solutions were found out by alkalimetric titration using phenolphthalein indicator. In the case of sulphate form of the resin, an attempt was made to estimate the exchanged SO₄²⁻ ion in the equilibrium solution by titrating it with standard BaCl₂ solution using Na-Rhodizonate adsorption indicator^{1,2}. But concentration of SO₄²⁻ ion was so low that it could not be estimated by this method.

For the chromate form of the resin, the equilibrium acid solutions were completely colourless, whereas it was found that K₂Cr₂O₇ solution, even at so low a concentration as 0.0001*N*, shows a distinct colour. This indicates that even if any dichromate ion is present in the solution due to ion-exchange, its concentration must be less than 0.0001*N*, which would give the ion-exchange value less than 0.005 meq per gm of dry resin.

In the case of nitrate form of the resin, the estimation of exchanged ion was not attempted due to non-availability of any simple suitable analytical method for its estimation.

The molecular adsorption of an acid was calculated from the difference between initial and final concentrations of the acid.

All the experiments were done in room temperatures (30 ± 2°).

Results and Discussions

Molecular adsorption isotherms of the acids (i.e.; formic, acetic, propionic, n-butyric, mono- and dichloroacetic acids and hydrochloric acid) on the respective anion forms of the Amberlite-IRA-400, are presented in figure 1. It is found that, molecular adsorption increases in the order, HCl < formic < acetic < propionic < n-butyric < monochloroacetic < dichloroacetic. The order of molecular adsorption for the carboxylic acids is a function of the chainlength of the acids. The result is in agreement with the findings of Schneider, Kresheck and Scheraga^{1,2}, who evaluated the thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of carboxylic fatty acids on a hydrocarbon network polystyrene. Their data indicate that the molecular adsorption of hydrocarbon chains of fatty acids takes place by a mechanism involving a decrease in the structure of water. But if the structure breaking of water is the

Fig. 1. Adsorption Isotherms of acids on the corresponding anion forms of Amberlite-IRA-400.

1. Formic acid on formate form., 2. Acetic acid on acetate form., 3. Propionic acid on propionate form., 4. n-butyric acid on n-butyrate form., 5. Mono chloro acetic acid on monochloro-acetate form., 6. Dichloro acetic acid on dichloro acetate form., 7. HCL on chloride form.

only cause for increasing adsorption with increase in chainlength, the large adsorption of mono- and dichloroacetic acids can not be explained. The same authors^{1,5} found that in homologous series of acids ranging from formic to n-butyric, only the undissociated form of the acids and not the dissociated carboxylate anions are adsorbed from aqueous solutions. The adsorption of the strong acid, i.e ; HCl, is also very small. The dissociation constants^{1,5} of monochloro- and dichloroacetic acids are 1.40×10^{-3} and 3.32×10^{-2} respectively, whereas that of acetic acid is 1.76×10^{-5} . From the standpoint of both structure breaking property, as well as dissociation constant, the adsorption of chlorosubstituted acetic acids should have been smaller than acetic acid. Samuelson, Soldatov and Thornton¹¹ observed large adsorptions of fluoro-acetic acids on the corresponding anion forms of an anion-exchange resin. They explained the large adsorptions of fluoro-acetic acids from the point of view of formation of hydrogen bonding of nondissociated acids to the counter-ions inside the resin. Possibly the same mechanism is responsible for the large adsorption of the chloro-acetic acids.

Molecular adsorption isotherms of the carboxylic acids (i.e., formic to n-butyric) by the sulphate and chromate forms of Amberlite-IRA-400, are given in figures 2 and 3. From these figures, molecular adsorptions are seen to increase in the order, formic < acetic < propionic < n-butyric for both the salt forms of the resin. In these salt forms of the resin, simultaneous ion-exchange and molecular adsorption might have been expected. But, as mentioned earlier, the ion-exchange was found to be almost nil within experimental error. This indicates that ion-exchange is not favoured by the anion-exchange resin containing multivalent counter-ion. The counter-ion associates

Fig. 2. Adsorption Isotherms of Carboxylic acids on the Sulphate form of Amberlite-IRA-400.

Fig. 3. Adsorption Isotherm of Carboxylic acids on the Chromate form of Amberlite-IRA-400.

partly with the hydrogen ion of the penetrating acid and in consequence, there is decrease in the charge of the original counter-ion and ionic groups of the resin become available for holding the anions of the penetrating acids. As a result, the acid is simply adsorbed without exchange of the counter-anion. This mechanism is known as site sharing^{1,4}.

Fig. 4. Adsorption Isotherms of Carboxylic acids on the nitrate form of Amberlite-IRA-400.

With the nitrate form of the resin, the same order of molecular adsorption for the carboxylic acids have been found, as is shown in figure 4.

Fig. 5. Molecular adsorption Isotherms of formic acid on Amberlite-IRA-400.

Ion-exchange isotherms of formic acid by the various resin salts are shown in fig. 5. For all other acids similar graphs can be shown. From these graphs, following results are obtained.

TABLE-1

Acids	Order of molecular adsorption
Formic	$RNO_3 < HCOOR < R_2SO_4 < R_2CrO_4$
Acetic	$RNO_3 < CH_3COOR < R_2SO_4 < R_2CrO_4$
Propionic	$RNO_3 < CH_3CH_2COOR \approx R_2SO_4 < R_2CrO_4$
n-butyric	$RNO_3 < R_2SO_4 < CH_3CH_2CH_2COOR < R_2CrO_4$

R=Resin matrix.

It is found that all the acids are most strongly held by the chromate form and most weakly by the nitrate form of the resin. For formic, acetic, propionic acids, position of the respective carboxylate form of the resin lies between nitrate and sulphate forms, whereas in the case of n-butyric acid, the position of the n-butyrate form is between sulphate and chromate forms.

Starobinets *et al*^{3,6} showed that stronger is the electrostatic interaction between the ion fixed and the opposite ion, the weaker is the carboxylate group attracted by the resin matrix and consequently the molecular adsorption is smaller. The order of the selectivity of the anions for the anion-exchange resin is¹⁴

From the selectivity order, it is seen that SO_4^{2-} has the largest selectivity among other ions given here. So molecular adsorption is expected to be lowest in

sulphate form of the resin. But from the results obtained as above, it is found that molecular adsorption is higher in sulphate and chromate forms than those in nitrate and carboxylate forms of the resin. So here the electrostatic interaction is not the main factor.

It has been already mentioned that, ion-exchange resin with multivalent counter-ions favours the adsorption of carboxylic acids by a mechanism involving site sharing¹⁴. So it may be expected that, inspite of electrostatic interactions, the acids are strongly held by the sulphate and chromate forms of the anion-exchange resin due to site sharing. It is also found that the order of adsorption by the two forms of the resin is $R_2SO_4 < R_2CrO_4$ for all the acids. The electrostatic interaction between the resin matrix and the counter-anion is higher for SO_4^{2-} ion than for CrO_4^{2-} ion. So here molecular adsorption is less in R_2SO_4 than in R_2CrO_4 . The fact, that the molecular adsorption by carboxylate forms is larger by nitrate forms, is due to the presence of larger number of carbon atoms present in the anion-exchange resin and also due to formation of hydrogen bonding¹¹.

References

- D. REICHENBERG and F. WALL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 3364.
- G. L. STAROBINETS and O. F. KHAREVICH, *Dokl. Akad. Nauk. BSSR*, 1965, 9(8), 516.
- M. J. MEHTA, R. A. BHATT, R. S. HEGDE, D. J. PATEL and S. L. BAFNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46(2), 130.
- M. J. MEHTA, R. A. BHATT and S. L. BAFNA, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.*, 1970, 33(2), 117.
- M. J. MEHTA, R. A. BHATT, R. S. HEGDE, D. J. PATEL and S. L. BAFNA, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1970, 33(2), 121.
- G. L. STAROBINETS and I. F. GLEIM, *Russ. J. of Phys Chem.*, 1965, 39(9), 1166.
- G. L. STAROBINETS, I. F. GLEIM, S. G. ALENITSKAYA, TEOR. IONNOGO OBMENA KHROMATOGR, *Tr. Vses. Nauch-Tech. Kouf.*, 1965, 73.
- G. L. STAROBINETS and S. G. ALENITSKAYA, *Russ. J. of Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 43(3), 390.
- G. L. STAROBINETS and S. G. ALENITSKAYA, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1969, 43(9), 2306.
- G. L. STAROBINETS and S. G. ALENITSKAYA, *Vestsi. Akad. Navuk, BSSR, Ser. Khim. Navuk.*, 1967, (1), 28.
- OLOF SAMUELSON, V. SOLDATOV and D. THORNTON, *Chem. Ser.*, 1973, 4(2), 89.
- A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd edn. (Longmans Green and Co., London), 1962.
- H. SCHNEIDER, G. C. KRESHECK and H. A. SCHERAGA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, 69, 1310.
- F. HELFFERICH, "Ion Exchange" (McGraw-Hill, New York), 1962.
- R. C. WEAST, "Handbook of Chemistry and Physics"; Chem. Rubber Co.; 52nd edn. 1971-1972 p. D120.